

Improved delineation of the Gassum Formation reservoir zones using seismic impedance inversions: implications for exploiting the Stenlille aquifer gas storage facility as a CO₂ storage demonstration site, onshore Denmark

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Abstract: A quantitative seismic interpretation of the Gassum Formation at the onshore aquifer gas storage near the Danish town of Stenlille is presented with its implications for exploiting the gas storage facility as a potential CO₂ demonstration site. Our objective was to better outline the reservoir heterogeneity of the Gassum Formation based on a 3D seismic volume and 20 wells available from the Stenlille gas storage facility. We derived new absolute and relative P-impedance inversion products, which are useful for delineating lithological distributions of thin sandstone reservoirs and shaly beds within the Gassum Formation. Our results broadly agree with previously published seismic interpretations, and build upon these by the identification of deviations in parts of the Gassum interval that should be considered in any subsequent development of a static reservoir model. Hence, this work is an important contribution to the planning of drilling new CO₂ injection wells as part of the development and management of the Stenlille CO₂ storage demonstration site. Nevertheless, we also recommend a modern seismic reprocessing of the 3D seismic data combined with newly acquired 2D data from the Stenlille structure as input into further quantitative seismic interpretation studies to refine reservoir characterization and reduce associated uncertainties.

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The Danish government has committed to a target of 70% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions in Denmark by 2030, and net-zero emissions by 2050. Geological CO₂ storage is regarded as a critical element for achieving these ambitious goals. Based on previous assessments, the estimated geological CO₂ storage capacity is c. 22 000 million tons, and more than 100 geological structures as potential CO₂ storage sites have been identified onshore and offshore (Anthonson *et al.* 2016). In this regard, the Stenlille aquifer natural gas storage facility in Denmark has received increasing attention as a potential first demonstration site for onshore CO₂ storage into the Upper Triassic–lowermost Jurassic Gassum Formation (Fig. 1a–c). This is because the Stenlille gas storage facility has been operated safely for more than 30 years, and is covered by comprehensive geophysical and operational data (Fig. 1d, e). However, despite all the available subsurface data, the spatial reservoir heterogeneity within the Gassum Formation is poorly outlined, which makes it more difficult to plan new CO₂ injection wells and for monitoring the CO₂ plume at various reservoir levels.

The Stenlille facility is proposed as a CO₂ storage demonstration site, prompting the publication of several studies based on the available 3D post-stack seismic and well-log data to revise and update the reservoir model of the Gassum Formation. For example, Gregersen *et al.* (2022) presented the tectonostratigraphic and structural evolution of the Stenlille structure based on seismic interpretations of the Stenlille 3D seismic cube and regional 2D lines. Smit *et al.* (2022) performed an integrated seismic geomorphological analysis and identified four major depositional environments. Lorentzen *et al.* (2022) presented a convolutional neural network trained on synthetic seismic data (Wu *et al.* 2019) to predict fault lineaments. Furthermore, various quantitative seismic interpretation studies have also been conducted recently. For

example, Bredeesen (2022) performed rock physics and fluid substitution modelling based on Stenlille well-log data and delineated the distributions of injected natural gas from a Bayesian litho-fluid seismic inversion (Kolbjørnsen *et al.* 2020). Chopra *et al.* (2022c) demonstrated an alternative phase decomposition technique to detect gas distributions based on the Stenlille data. Chopra *et al.* (2022b) inverted the seismic data for P-impedance from a low-frequency model, and used that to derive porosities, gamma-ray and water saturation from a multi-attribute regression analysis (Ray and Chopra 2015, 2016). Chopra *et al.* (2022a) compared and extended these results using unsupervised machine learning tools for the determination of litho-fluid facies, such as principal component analysis, self-organizing mapping and generative topographical mapping.

Despite all the recently published quantitative interpretation studies from Stenlille, they are prone to uncertainties due to limited seismic resolution, signal-to-noise ratio and pre-stack data unavailability. One of the remaining key problems at Stenlille is to de-risk the lithological distributions of interchanging sandstone reservoirs and impermeable shaly zones, as well making a robust interpretation of the top Gassum Formation. This information is important in an assessment of various CO₂ injection strategies at Stenlille. For example, one option is to inject and store CO₂ within one of the sandstone reservoir zones that have shown ineffective production withdrawal rates of natural gas due to tighter reservoirs. Another option is to use a reservoir zone not exploited for gas storage previously. Deciding the final CO₂ injection strategy will therefore rely on a good static reservoir model containing lithological distributions.

The main objectives of this paper were to apply relative seismic inversions and an absolute Bayesian litho-fluid classification similar to that in Bredeesen (2022) to discriminate between

Fig. 1. Location maps showing: (a) identified CO₂ structures in the Danish area relevant for CO₂ storage within different formations (modified from Hjelm *et al.* 2020); (b) the Sjælland island with the Havnsø prospect outlined; (c) the Stenlille area with well positions and the 3D seismic survey (Bredesen 2022) indicated; (d) the Stenlille structure with two horizon surfaces bounding the Gassum reservoir target plotted together with seismic sections and four wells in 3D view; and (e) net gas volume history in Zone 1-3 and Zone 5 relative to the acquisition of the wells and the 3D seismic survey (from Bredesen 2022).

sandstones and shales exhibiting separable P-impedances. These results are useful for outlining the reservoir heterogeneities and to interpret a reliable seismic horizon more accurately for the top Gassum Formation. The results are then compared to other published litho-facies prediction studies from Stenlille, where observed discrepancies are discussed with regard to building a representative static reservoir model.

Although the various seismic inversion results have undeniably been helpful for improving the reservoir characterization of the Gassum Formation at Stenlille, the subsurface data are outdated with limited signal-to-noise ratio and data content. Hence, state-of-the-art seismic reprocessing is recommended to refine the seismic image and provide pre-stack seismic data for more robust quantitative seismic interpretation studies. Moreover, new 2D seismic lines were acquired in 2022 that tie to the existing Stenlille data and extend north, and cover a 2D grid over the nearby and yet undrilled Havnsø CO₂ storage prospect (Fig. 1b). Because the Gassum Formation at Stenlille is used as a nearby reservoir analogue, we anticipate and advise that future quantitative seismic

interpretations should be based on a reprocessed seismic 3D volume from Stenlille combined with the new 2D survey to further reduce the risk at nearby CO₂ storage sites.

Data coverage and geological setting

In Denmark, two operating subsurface gas storage facilities serve as a buffer for the supply and demand of natural gas from the North Sea. The first is located in salt caverns in Jylland. The other is a saline aquifer near the town of Stenlille (Fig. 1) at a depth of 1500 m with temperatures of 40–45°C and around 150 bar of reservoir pressure (Laier and Øbro 2009). Natural gas has been injected and stored at Stenlille since 1989 (Fig. 1e), where the reservoir occurs within a domal subsurface structure and is covered by a tight cap rock. The Upper Triassic–lowermost Jurassic Gassum Formation consists of interbedded sandstones and shales that host the injected gas by displacing formation water (Fig. 2). The sandstones were deposited within fluvial and nearshore marine environments, whereas the shales represent deep marine and lagoonal environments. These yield

Fig. 2. (a) Illustration of the gas storage play concept at Stenlille from Laier and Øbro (2009). (b) Reconstructed section from (a) within the available 3D seismic post-stack volume with gamma-ray curves superimposed from various wells. (c) The upper target horizon with the seismic section from (b) plotted as a grey line. TWT, two-way time.

various lithofacies such as channelized and sheet sands, and widespread shales draping over the landscapes (Nielsen 2003). The Gassum Formation is *c.* 140 m thick but only the upper 40 m is used for storage within two separate units, namely Zone 1-3 and Zone 5 (Fig. 2). Overlying the Gassum Formation is the *c.* 300 m-thick Lower Jurassic Fjerritslev Formation that acts as a regional cap rock. The storage capacity at the Stenlille site has been estimated to be 3×10^9 m³ of gas but due to reservoir heterogeneity the gas is distributed in several separate zones (Laier and Øbro 2009). The subsurface gas storage is accessed via 14 injection and withdrawal wells drilled from three separate surface platforms, and six observation wells located at the fringes of the structure.

The Stenlille gas storage structure was initially identified from 2D seismic data but the subsequent acquisition of a 3D seismic survey from 1997, and well data from 20 injection, production and observation wells, has yielded a good understanding of the subsurface (Laier and Øbro 2009; Kristensen *et al.* 2016; Weibel *et al.* 2017). However, the dataset has some limitations; the 3D seismic data covers *c.* 43 surface km² of full-fold data (56.4 km² total size) and was acquired back in 1997, with limited signal-to-noise ratio, lack of pre-stack data, and large variations in the availability and quality of consistent well-log measurements. This sets some constraints for applying quantitative seismic interpretation tools, as it is more challenging to derive a set of reservoir variables (porosity, shale volume, pore fluid saturations and lithofacies) from a single post-stack volume that is primarily governed by P-impedance contrasts (Shuey 1985). However, if we consider the main types of litho-fluid classes (LFCs) present within the Gassum interval at Stenlille, we can make some reasonable LFC categorizations based only on P-impedance. This can be seen in Figure 3, which shows a suite of log curves from the Stenlille-17 (ST17) and Stenlille-18 (ST18) wells and a P-impedance distribution plot for water- and gas-saturated sandstones and shales. Both of these wells were drilled 1 year prior to the 3D seismic survey and are therefore approximately comparable with respect to the net gas volumes *in situ* (Bredesen 2022) (Fig. 1e). The P-impedance (AI) varies proportionally and inversely proportionally to the gas saturations and shale volumes, respectively. Hence,

within a confined interval covering the Gassum reservoir target, the various P-impedance properties can be associated with some distinctive LFCs.

Well-tie analysis

Reliable well-tie results are important to quality check (QC) the interpreted horizons and inversion results, and for calibrating a single wavelet for the seismic inversion that is expected to be temporally and spatially invariant. All 20 wells at Stenlille cover the Gassum target interval, and 12 include sonic and density logs within the 3D survey (ST1, ST2, ST4, ST5, ST6, ST9, ST10, ST11, ST14, ST15, ST17, ST18 and ST19 wells) with varying log lengths. Hence, a zero-phase statistical wavelet was extracted from a 525 ms time window extending beyond the Gassum interval while simultaneously avoiding strong contrasts outside our target, containing dominating frequencies between 25 and 80 Hz. Average maximum cross-correlation coefficients exceeding 0.8 for the Gassum target interval were obtained for the ST1, ST2, ST5, ST10 and ST11 wells, where the best well ties were obtained in ST1 and ST2 with an 88% match between synthetic and real traces.

Figure 4 shows a well-tie QC plot for ST18 covering the Gassum target interval, with P-impedance log (AI) (Fig. 4a), gamma-ray log (GR) (Fig. 4b), caliber log (Fig. 4c), synthetic trace (Fig. 4d), seismic trace (Fig. 4e), seismic cross-section intersecting the well (where an average maximum cross-correlation of 0.64 was obtained) (Fig. 4f), the statistical wavelet (Fig. 4g) and the seismic frequency spectrum from the wavelet extraction window (Fig. 4h). The upper and base target horizons, as well as three tops of reservoir sand zones (top zones 1, 3 and 5 of the Gassum Formation), are included as references. The sand-dominated layers (low GR) are apparently characterized by lower AI than the shale-dominated layers (high GR), which seems to correlate with some of the peak events in the seismic traces. The caliber log shows a larger borehole size in the Fjerritslev Formation, which may be due to washout and caving of the mudstones that can influence other log measurements. For example, an abnormally high AI anomaly appears right below the upper target horizon within the lower part of

Fig. 3. Suite of well logs for (a) Stenlille-17 and (b) Stenlille-18, depicting from left to right: the acoustic impedance (AI), porosity, shale volume and water-saturation curves. The various reservoir zones are labelled to the right. (c) A histogram plot showing the distribution of the AI for various litho-fluid classes (LFCs).

Fig. 4. Correlation of the Stenlille-18 well logs with the seismic data. The tops for Zone 1, Zone 3 and Zone 5 sand are included for reference. An average maximum cross-correlation coefficient of 0.64 was obtained in the target interval using the statistical wavelet for the synthetic seismogram.

the Fjerritslev Formation. This anomaly causes a poor tie in the lower part of the Fjerritslev Formation as seen when comparing the synthetic and seismic traces.

The ST18 well is one of several wells with lower correlation coefficients that are located close to predicted fault lineaments. To investigate whether poorer well-tie cross-correlation results could more generally be associated with possible fault patterns, all the well-path projections were plotted onto a fault attribute map. Figure 5 shows high-probability fault lineaments from a machine learning approach (Wu *et al.* 2019) across: (a) the upper target horizon with the various well paths plotted on top; and (b) along a cross-line intersecting the ST18 well path. All the wells that appear to intersect with any of the fault lineaments at the Gassum target level seem to systematically yield lower cross-correlation

coefficients than the wells not interfering with the faults (ST1, ST2, ST5, ST10 and ST11 wells). Hence, suboptimal seismic images across fault planes may influence the well-to-seismic correlation, as reflected by the well-tie correlation table (Fig. 5) for a selection of the wells. These implications should be taken into consideration when evaluating the seismic inversion results at various well locations.

From interface to layer properties

In this section we consider different seismic inversion approaches to transform the interface properties (travel time, amplitudes and reflectivities) as measured by seismic reflection data into layer properties (e.g. acoustic impedance, velocity and LFCs) to improve

Fig. 5. (a) A fault probability attribute map derived from a machine learning approach (Wu *et al.* 2019) from the upper part of the Gassum interval with the well-path projections plotted on top. Blue dots are the locations of vertical wells, whereas the deviated well paths are shown by the black curves extending out from the well heads (green dots). Elevation iso-contours represent the upper target horizon (Fig. 2c). Well-tie correlation coefficients for a selection of the wells are shown in the table next to the map. (b) A cross-section through the 3D volume intersecting the Stenlille-18 (ST18) well path (intersecting red dotted line on the map).

reservoir characterization. Seismic inversions can provide more detailed and high-resolution images for reservoir characterization by better balancing the seismic frequencies and by compensating for geophysical artefacts such as seismic tuning (Pendrel 2001; Bosch *et al.* 2010). Three different approaches are considered here: (1) trace integration (TI) (Latimer *et al.* 2000); (2) coloured inversion (CI) (Lancaster and Whitcombe 2000; Blouin and Gloaguen 2017); and (3) a Bayesian (or probabilistic) seismic inversion for litho-fluid classification (Buland *et al.* 2008; Kolbjørnsen *et al.* 2020).

Relative impedance inversions

Both the TI and CI approaches yield relative impedance where the aim is to shape the seismic data to look more like layers rather than interface properties, without including a prior model. These methods are not meant to be final products in a reservoir characterization workflow based on inversion results but they are valuable starting points, or sanity checks, because they are quick, easily accessible, completely deterministic and have been demonstrated to work in many cases (Chopra and Marfurt 2006; Hall 2009). The TI method simply represents a sample-by-sample cumulative sum of amplitudes down the seismic trace, which in effect rotates the phase of the data by -90° . As such, the amplitude energy is shifted from the layer interfaces that exhibit high-frequency information into the layers that have lower-frequency components. The CI approach works in a similar manner by attempting to make seismic data appear more like acoustic layer properties as measured by acoustic well-log data. By applying a CI operator to the seismic data, it shapes the seismic spectrum to approach the well-log spectrum and applies a -90° phase rotation. As for the trace integration, the CI is not guided by any prior information and is completely driven by the band-limited seismic data.

Figure 6 shows the derived TI and CI sections along the same arbitrary line as presented in the studies of Bredeesen (2022) and

Chopra *et al.* (2022b), with shale volume curves plotted on top for the intersecting wells (from left to right: ST15, ST4, ST19, ST2, ST5, ST1 and ST10). The TI and CI represent relative changes in acoustic impedance (RAI); orange and blue colours refer to increasing and decreasing acoustic impedance, respectively. Compared to the seismic data, these RAI sections appear to resolve the layers better between the upper and base target horizons. The TI seems to yield slightly better resolution than the CI, possibly because the CI operator length and frequency bandwidth specification tends to boost some of the low- and high-frequency noise. In general, higher log shale volumes correlate with increasing RAI.

For a closer quality check of the RAI along a wellbore, Figure 7 shows the porosity (Fig. 7a), shale volume (Fig. 7b), water saturation (Fig. 7c) and acoustic impedance logs from the ST18 well, with single traces from the TI (orange) (Fig. 7d) and CI (green) (Fig. 7e) volumes plotted on top and an intersecting seismic section (Fig. 7f). In general, both the TI and CI results correlate well with the AI trend, where we see that the CI tends to be somewhat smoother and thereby lower resolution than the TI attribute. Recall that the AI logs and RAI volumes represent absolute and relative properties, respectively, and therefore can only be compared in a qualitative manner. Also, the difference in frequency content becomes more apparent where the TI and CI traces appear as smooth versions of the AI log due to the limited seismic bandwidth. Some of the distinctive high-AI layers within the Gassum Formation interval between Zone 1 and Zone 6 are certainly strongly correlated with the more shaly beds, such as the Zone 4, Zone 5 clay and Zone 6 clay layers, which are 7, 5 and 8 m thick in the ST18 well, respectively.

A video is included in the Supplementary material, with the TI surface extracted along the upper target horizon that is time shifted downwards, starting at 0 and ending at 100 ms below the horizon in 2 ms steps. The ST1, ST5, ST10, ST15 and ST18 wells are included as a reference in the 3D view and with a greyscale seismic backdrop.

Fig. 6. Arbitrary seismic sections showing: (a) post-stack seismic data; (b) trace integration; (c) coloured inversion; and (d) map view of the upper target with the black line representing the arbitrary section. Shale volume log curves are superimposed. TWT, two-way time.

Fig. 7. Trace integration and coloured inversion results compared to Stenille-18 (ST18) well-log data and a seismic cross-section.

The horizon probing down through the target interval reveals the lateral distributions of the various lithologies and even some fluid effects from the injected natural gas, which appear as blue anomalies at around 20–22 ms (Zone 3) and 36–40 ms (Zone 5) that are characterized by low acoustic impedance (Bredesen 2022).

Bayesian post-stack seismic inversion for litho-facies classification

The RAI approaches described above do not allow interpretation of absolute layer properties or the incorporation of prior information to guide the inversion where the seismic data may contain limited information. Hence, we apply a more rigorous inversion approach as described by Buland *et al.* (2008), Kolbjørnsen *et al.* (2016) and Kolbjørnsen *et al.* (2020). Figure 8 shows a schematic set-up of the inversion workflow.

A simple inversion set-up is considered to reduce the non-uniqueness of the highly inverse problem with only post-stack data available as a function of contrasting P-impedance layers. For simplicity, only three LFCs were defined, as follows: (1) shales with high P-impedance; (2) gas-saturated sandstones with low P-impedance; and (3) water-saturated sandstones with intermediate P-impedance. The P-impedance can be broken down into the P-velocity and density properties (Fig. 9a) where the different LFCs are defined in the P-velocity v. density domain (Fig. 9b). Each LFC is defined by statistical mean values, standard deviations and correlations between the P-velocity and density extracted from different depth zones in the well logs. For the Bayesian inversion, Gaussian distributions are estimated from the statistical parameters to represent the rock physics likelihood models for each LFC. The goal by defining the various LFCs is to capture various lithologies and fluid scenarios that exhibit distinctive elastic properties in specific intervals bounded by seismic horizons. To distinguish the various LFCs there must be sufficient elastic contrasts between them, as this is what governs the seismic response. Hence, the more

overlap there is between the different LFCs in Figure 9b, the more difficult it is for the seismic inversion to separate them. The prior probabilities were set equal (i.e. 33.3%) for each of the LFCs within the Gassum interval to allow the information in the seismic data to express itself. In addition to the LFCs within the Gassum Formation interval, LFCs for the Fjerritslev and Vinding formations were also incorporated into the prior model to represent the overburden and underburden, respectively.

After the LFC definition, a Markov chain model (Fig. 8) mixed various vertical combinations of LFC ‘microblocks’ corresponding to the seismic sampling, which is 2 ms in this study. The reflectivities can then be calculated from the rock physics properties of the LFCs (Fig. 9b) before being convolved with a wavelet and finally compared to some seismic traces within a specific time window. High probabilities are calculated when a synthetic trace yields a good match to a measured trace (i.e. minimal residual). At each LFC transition (or interface) within a specific window, reflections are forced into the inversion results such that thin layers below tuning thickness can be investigated.

Figure 10a shows the posterior probability results plotted on top of the seismic data for the shale LFC, represented by the black–yellow colour range, and the probability of a gas sandstone exceeding 70% is represented by a white mask. Figure 10b shows the litho-facies classification results as presented in Chopra *et al.* (2022b). The shale volume logs and tops for reservoir Zone 1 and Zone 6 sand are included at each well as reference points. Whereas the inversion in this study only distinguishes between three LFCs based on contrasts in P-impedance, Chopra *et al.* (2022b) derived porosity and GR volumes from multi-attribute regression analysis (Hampson *et al.* 2001; Pramanik *et al.* 2004) that were used to classify six groups of varying porosity and GR without taking into account water-saturation variations. Although the two inversion methods are different, the high shale probabilities agree with the predicted shales and shaly sands from Chopra *et al.* (2022b) and likewise for the more sandstone-dominated zones.

Fig. 8. Schematic workflow diagram for the Bayesian seismic inversion for classification of different litho-fluid classes (LFCs). PSTM, pre-stack time migration.

There are also some interesting differences between the two inversion results, such as right below the upper target horizon where [Chopra et al. \(2022b\)](#) predicted a thicker homogenous shale layer, corresponding to the lower part of the Fjerritslev cap rock associated with mudstones. In contrast, our inversion results indicate that that this upper shale layer is divided into two separate units in some parts of the seismic. Hence, it appears that our inversion, in part, manages to resolve Zone 1, which is not the case in [Chopra et al. \(2022b\)](#). [Figure 10d](#) shows a close-up view around the top structure at the ST19 and ST2 (black dashed rectangle in [Fig. 10c](#)) wells, with some interpretation of the reservoir zonation. Note that the ST19 well tie in the upper part of the Gassum interval was moderate and could possibly be

shifted somewhat upwards to match the inversion results better. Although the shale LFC probabilities exhibit as somewhat patchy and overlie thick shale layers, overall they look consistent with the shale volume logs. Also note how high gas probabilities primarily appear within Zone 3 and Zone 5 sandstones, and to some extent in Zone 1 at ST2.

[Figure 11](#) shows a similar plot to [Figure 7](#) along the ST18 well but with the absolute inversion results included, both represented by single traces as virtual logs and as intersecting cross-sections. There are several implications from this plot, including:

- The TI and absolute inversion are strongly correlated. For example, an increase in the TI generally agrees with high

Fig. 9. (a) A 3D scatter plot showing the relationships between P-velocity, density, P-impedance and shale volume within the Gassum Formation in ST17, ST18 and ST19 wells. (b) Rock physics likelihood models for three different LFCs considered within the Gassum interval estimated by Gaussian distributions from well-log data. The LFCs are plotted from a stochastic simulation (1000 data points) based on statistical parameters and with some density iso-contour lines projected on top.

Fig. 10. Absolute post-stack inversion results plotted on top as overlays and masks onto the seismic arbitrary line (Fig. 6a): (a) the shale probability (colourbar) and gas sandstone probability exceeding 70% (white mask); and (b) the litho-facies classification as presented in Chopra *et al.* (2022b). The log curves represent the shale volume. TWT, two-way time.

shale probability, indicating that the seismic data are primarily driving the inversion rather than the prior model.

- The seismic peak reflection events (Fig. 11f) approximately correspond to the \pm zero crossings (going from orange to blue) of the TI (Fig. 11g). The top of Zone 1 (i.e. Top Gassum Formation) therefore seems to be appropriately approximated by picking and tracking along the upper black peak (Fig. 11f). This position of the Top Gassum is also supported by the gas probability as it is approximately at the

top of the Zone 1 gas sand probability from the inversion (Fig. 10).

- The water sandstone LFC does not stand out with particularly high probabilities within the water sandstone intervals (in particular, the lower part of Zone 5 and in Zone 6). For example, within the water-saturated part of Zone 5 sand and in Zone 6 sand, the inversion is more certain that these intervals are sandstones rather than shales but it cannot differentiate between the water- and gas-saturated scenarios

Fig. 11. Comparison of the relative and absolute inversions at the Stenlille-18 well: (a) porosity; (b) shale volume; (c) water saturation; (d) acoustic impedance log and seismic trace integration (orange); (e) LFC probabilities (green, gas sandstone; brown, shale; blue, water sandstone) that sums up to 1 at each depth sample; and intersecting cross-sections of (f) seismic data, (g) trace integration, (h) shale probability, (i) gas sandstone probability and (j) the lithofacies interpretation in Chopra *et al.* (2022b). The dashed vertical black line represents the well locations.

Fig. 12. Interpreting reservoir zonation based on the trace integration attribute. TWT, two-way time.

where the LFCs overlap and the AI is around $7000 \text{ km s}^{-1} \times \text{g cm}^{-3}$ (Fig. 3c). Hence, it is useful to quality check the inversion results by comparing the posterior probabilities from the various LFCs relative to the prior probabilities.

- In addition, the false gas anomalies within Zone 6 were also observed and reported in Bredeesen (2022). However, these probabilities are on average lower (<70%) compared to the probabilities where gas is actually stored between Zone 1 and Zone 5 (see the water-saturation log).

Due to the high correlation between the TI attribute and absolute inversion results, the TI attribute may yield a useful volume to interpret some of the reservoir zonation boundaries by picking and tracking along the zero crossings. Figure 12 shows some interpretations of the various reservoir zones based on a 3D autotracker picked on the zero-crossing events in the TI volume along the arbitrary section. The horizons are in a reasonable agreement with the shale volume logs and could yield a good representation of the zonation boundaries.

Discussion

The reservoir heterogeneity distribution within the Gassum Formation at the Stenlille aquifer gas storage is poorly delineated, making it challenging to accurately de-risk the CO₂ storage prospectivity. The main objective of this study was therefore to unravel the reservoir zonation using modern seismic analysis based

on the available 3D seismic volume from 1997. However, because the only volume data available were post-stack data governed by acoustic impedance (AI) contrasts, the quantitative interpretations of reservoir and pore fluid variations from the seismic amplitudes would be influenced by higher non-uniqueness. Figure 13 shows a cross-plot of AI v. V_p/V_s from the ST19 well covering the Gassum Formation interval. The data are coloured according to porosity, shale volume and water-saturation variations for investigating some of the seismic-reservoir relationships. It shows that all of these parameters have an influence on the AI along the x-axis but there is an inherent ambiguity when trying to distinguish which of these parameters are causing a certain change in the AI. For example, if a decrease in the AI is observed, it cannot be deduced whether this is caused by higher porosities, cleaner sands, fizz gas or some combination of these. However, if the V_p/V_s information along the y-axis is also considered, we can better discriminate between these parameters. It is, therefore, advisable to reprocess the 3D Stenlille data using modern processing techniques, not only to improve the seismic image quality but also to derive pre-stack migrated gathers for a subsequent amplitude variation with offset (AVO) inversion that could improve the reservoir characterization results beyond exclusively using post-stack data.

The differences in the inversion results demonstrated in this study and in Chopra *et al.* (2022b) could in part be explained by the various underlying prior models used. The ‘blocky’ Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) model used here (Larsen *et al.* 2006; Sen and Biswas 2017; de Figueiredo *et al.* 2019; Kolbjørnsen *et al.* 2020; Hansen 2021) generally works well for identifying thin layers and

Fig. 13. Cross-plot of acoustic impedance v. P/S velocity ratio (V_p/V_s) data from the Stenlille-19 (ST19) well for the Gassum sandstone reservoir colour coded with (a) porosity, (b) shale volume and (c) water saturation. From Bredeesen (2022).

Fig. 14. 1D blocky seismic modelling: (a) P-velocity and (b) density logs from the Stenlille-2 (ST2) well; (c) synthetic trace, seismic response as a function of (d) wedge modelling of varying Zone 1 thicknesses. Dashed cyan and pink lines represent the top and base of Zone 1, respectively. TWT, two-way time; OB, overburden; UB, underburden.

sharp boundaries. *Chopra et al. (2022b)*, however, used a low-frequency model with a log-normal assumption imposing smoothness (*Doyen 2007*), which limits the inversion results in the high-

frequency range by the seismic bandwidth where thin layers and sharp boundaries are smoothed out (*Bosch et al. 2010; Sen and Biswas 2017*). In general, inversions based on a smooth low-

Fig. 15. Schematic illustration of how seismic inversion results were integrated into a static reservoir model for the Stenlille site.

frequency starting model may perform well in more compaction-driven geological settings, whereas inversions built upon a MCMC model are more in harmony with blocky geology. Despite these differences, it seems like the impedance inversion in Chopra *et al.* (2022b) manages to resolve the thin low-impedance sandstones at Stenlille; but the subsequent Bayesian litho-facies classification based on the multi-attribute regression analysis tend to classify some sandstones, such as the Zone 1 sandstones, as shales (Figs 10 and 11).

The sandstone reservoirs and shaly beds are generally better resolved in the seismic inversion results in Figure 11g–i compared to the input post-stack seismic data in Figure 11f. However, when considering some of the thin zones, such as the ‘Zone 6 clay’, the inversion results imply much thicker layers than the formation top markers in the ST18 well. This is the apparent artefact of seismic tuning that can be illustrated by a simple wedge model. Figure 14 shows the blocky (or mean) P-velocity (Fig. 14a) and density (Fig. 14b) logs from Stenlille-2 next to an *in situ* synthetic trace (Fig. 14c) and the seismic response of varying thicknesses (i.e. the wedge model) (Fig. 14d) of Zone 1, which is 5 m thick in ST2, as illustrated by the black ellipse in Figure 14d. When tracking the orange peak event for Top Zone 1 towards decreasing thicknesses, we eventually see that the event tends to bend upwards from the actual wedge model (dashed cyan and pink lines) and overpredicts the Zone 1 thickness. Furthermore, the wedge model reveals how tuning effects influence the top and base events for Zone 1 for thicknesses up to around 20 m, where they stop to interfere with one another. Hence, although the seismic inversion volumes may reveal reservoir heterogeneities and zonation better, the results are still limited to the frequency bandwidth preserved within the seismic data.

The seismic inversion results are very useful in combination with seismic geomorphological workflows and core analysis from the Stenlille site (Nielsen 2003; Weibel *et al.* 2017) for delineating distributions of sands and shales, which is important input into the static reservoir model. Figure 15 shows a schematic illustration of how the relative and absolute seismic inversion results were used as input to better delineate and populate a static reservoir model for Stenlille. The Stenlille reservoir management team can subsequently use these results to better outline a robust CO₂ storage and natural gas injection/withdrawal strategy, thereby better predicting fluid movements and migration pathways. In many cases one would create a static reservoir model based primarily on geostatistical realizations from the wells but using additional 3D seismic data exploits available for remote measurements that allow geological risks and uncertainties to be scrutinized between wells.

Conclusions

A quantitative interpretation of the Gassum Formation at the Stenlille aquifer gas storage is presented with its implications for exploiting the facility as a CO₂ storage demonstration site. Based on a 3D post-stack volume governed by P-impedance contrasts, relative and absolute P-impedance inversion products were derived with an improved resolution of thin sandstone reservoirs and shaly beds, which were useful for delineating their spatial distributions within the seismic 3D volume. These new details are important input for building a robust static reservoir model for subsequent CO₂ storage de-risking, development and management at Stenlille. Although the presented inversion results seems to improve the reservoir characterization, a modern seismic reprocessing is now advised for improved seismic imaging and to provide pre-stack gathers to constrain the non-uniqueness of the inversion results.

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